

HEAVY METALS IN DRY BOTTOM SOIL OF THE ARAL SEA AND THEIR MIGRATION

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Every year, up to one hundred million tons of toxic salt and dust mixture is carried by the winds from the dried bottom of the Aral Sea. Most of it settles in the nearest territories, but millions of tons are carried away thousands of kilometers away. The results of the analyzes show that the migration of toxicants infects the environment and pollutes plant products. Based on the results of the research, approaches have been developed to balance the ions in a layer of 0-20 cm to create the development of plants according to biological properties.

The dried bottom of the Aral Sea is a global threat to the environment. From this, one can imagine what a global difficult task faces scientists who are looking for possible ways to lay a dried-up seabed and help the natural process to fix sandy areas containing toxicants and devoid of vegetation [1-3]. A toxic salt-dust mixture is carried by the winds around the Aral Sea and its adjacent territory [2-4].

To study toxicants and their migration, the southeastern latitudes of the Aral Sea from the Muynok region were chosen as the object of study. The selected territory of the Aral Sea is located from the 80th kilometer from Muynak. Although this territory belongs to the drylands of the 60s, 70s and 80s, samples of soil layers and plant products grown in areas and areas adjacent to the territory of the island were taken for analysis.

It has been established that the composition of soil samples taken from the layers of the dry bottom of the island consists mainly of mineralized sandy layers (Fig. 1).

Salt content in the upper layer ranges from 15-20%, including chlorine 10-15%, sulfates 5-10%. The sharp excess of chlorine content over sulfate ions is explained by the accumulation of salts in soils under conditions of stagnant highly mineralized chloride-type groundwater. So in a layer of 20-40 cm, the salt

content in the paid residue decreases by 10-20%. In these horizons, the content of chlorine is 5-8% and sulfates - 2-3%. The value of dense remains from 40 cm to a depth of 90 cm varies mainly within 5-6%. The type of chemistry up to 60 cm is sulfate-sodium chloride alternating with sodium chloride. The increased moistening of the deep layers of the soil is a distinctive feature of saline.

The absorption capacity of clay saline soil under crust up to 60 cm is characterized by low and varies in examples 0-20 cm per 100 g of soil. The composition of the base in the soil layer up to 60 cm is dominated by calcium, then magnesium, sodium. The presence of sodium in the soil-absorbing complex indicates a sign of alkalinity, however, this phenomenon is not significant, since it is closely related to the content of silt particles on the profile of sections up to 90 cm, which content or varies between 2-12%. A pronounced saline feature in the soil is manifested when the content of silt particles in the composition of 50 cm is more than a percent.

Li 670.784 Rep: 2

Intensity: 1468116.9

1Conc: 0.076 mg/L

Al 396.153 Rep: 2

Intensity: -39681.0

2Conc: -0.023 mg/L

Mo 202.031 Rep: 2

Intensity: 2179.9

3Conc: 0.058 mg/L

Sb 206.836 Rep: 2

Intensity: -776.9

6Conc: 0.008 mg/L

Sn 189.927 Rep: 2

Intensity: -689.3

7Conc: 0.010 mg/L

Sr 407.771 Rep: 2

Intensity: 62128816.2

8Conc: 1.601 mg/L

Fig.1. Results of analyzes of metals in the composition on an Avio 200 ICP-OES optical emission spectrometer with inductively coupled plasma (Perkin Elmer, USA)

Also soil in the layers of metals Sb, Cd, Pb, Sn, Mo, Hg, B and other trace elements and toxic heavy metals are above the specified norm and not at the level of quantitative and equivalent norms. This has a negative effect on the absorption of appropriate nutrients by plants and on their growth and development.

Accordingly, in order to regulate the amount of elements in the soil in an equivalent ratio to the growth and development of plants, we tried to balance the composition of the soil of the seedling and seed planting site with nutrients in the plant development stage.

We calculated the number of elements in an equivalent ratio for adding per 100 g of soil: ammonium nitrate 171 mg/100 g; Ammophos 206 mg/100g; potassium sulfate 140 mg/100g; Cobalt sulfate 5.5 mg/100g; Boric acid 39 mg/100 g; Zinc sulfate 7.8 mg/100g; Ferrous sulfate 242 mg/100 g; Copper sulfate 15.6 mg/100g; Manganese sulfate 163 mg/100 g; Calcium sulfate 2700 mg/100g.

$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was used to improve the ratio of Ca and Na ions in the soil. The initial ratio of elements Ca and Na is 4.5:9.

After applying calcium fertilizers, the equivalent ratio of Ca and Na ions is 36:9.

Since monovalent elements destroy the soil structure, as a result of the introduction of additives, the concentration of Na^+ and Cl^- ions decreases

Due to the relatively low nitrogen content in the soil, 171 mg of ammonium nitrate, 206 mg of ammonium phosphate fertilizer due to lack of

phosphorus, 140 mg of potassium sulfate to equalize the amount of potassium, 242 mg of Fe_2SO_4 salt to normalize the amount of iron ions were applied to the soil. This amount of added salts is calculated to improve the condition of 100 g of soil compared to the Na ion in the soil.

Analysis of the soil layers on the dried bottom of the Aral Sea showed that the salt content in the upper layer ranges from 15-20%. To correct the amount of elements in the soil in the equivalent ratio of plant growth and development, we tried to balance the soil composition of the seedling planting site and seeds with nutrients at the stage of plant development.

Calculated the number of elements in an equivalent ratio for adding per 100 g of soil: ammonium nitrate 171 mg/100 g; $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{PO}_4$ 206 mg/100g; K_2SO_4 140 mg/100g; CoSO_4 5,5 mg/100g; H_3BO_3 39 mg/100 g; ZnSO_4 7,8 mg/100g; FeSO_4 242 mg/100 g; CuSO_4 15,6 mg/100g; MnSO_4 163 mg/100 g; CaSO_4 2700 mg/100g to create nutrition for plants in developmental stages.

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